

Pragmatic Autoethnography: Thoughts on why it may be needed

Autoethnography is a reflexive subjective narrative qualitative research method, both a product and a process, whereby the researcher ('auto') depicts ('graphy') their understanding of their lived experience within an ethnographic ('ethno') or socio-cultural context [1].

Autoethnographic approaches embrace the spirit of first person experiential story-telling from varying perspectives: '*evocative*' emphasizes feelings/emotions [2], '*analytic*' emphasizes the theoretical analysis of broader social phenomena [3], '*critical*' emphasizes critical theory. Personal, relational, cultural, and theoretical reflexivity is essential [4].

At the heart of pragmatism is actionable knowledge; inquiry is viewed as an experiential process, with experience, knowing, and acting interconnected [5]. Pragmatism favours multiple methodologies that 'work best' to understand specific issues, and generate and apply practical knowledge [6].

Autoethnography offers pragmatists an important methodology to reflect on their research. Nevertheless the use, or adaptation, of existing autoethnographic approaches may not 'work best' and risks 'method slurring' [7]. Moreover, while pragmatism is rooted in subjectivity, it differs ontologically and epistemologically from social constructionism.

A discrete '*pragmatic*' approach is thus suggested to support researcher deliberation on why, how, and to what effect they are investigating, acquiring, and applying knowledge within their research environment. The '*pragmatic*' emphasizes the experiential process of generating actionable knowledge.

References:

1. Ellis, C., Adams, T. E., & Bochner, A. P. (2011). Autoethnography: an overview. *Historical social research/Historische sozialforschung*, 273-290.
2. Ellis, C. (1997). Evocative autoethnography: Writing emotionally about our lives. *Representation and the text: Re-framing the narrative voice*, 115-139.
3. Anderson, L. (2006). Analytic autoethnography. *Journal of contemporary ethnography*, 35(4), 373-395.
4. Short, N. P., Turner, L., & Grant, A. (Eds.). (2013). *Contemporary British Autoethnography*. Springer Science & Business Media.
5. Kelly, L. M., & Cordeiro, M. (2020). Three principles of pragmatism for research on organizational processes. *Methodological innovations*, 13(2), 2059799120937242.
6. Kaushik, V., & Walsh, C. A. (2019). Pragmatism as a research paradigm and its implications for social work research. *Social sciences*, 8(9), 255.
7. Gonot-Schoupsinsky, F. N., & Garip, G. (2019). Differential qualitative analysis: a pragmatic qualitative methodology to support personalised healthcare research in heterogenous samples. *The Qualitative Report*, 24(12), 2997-3007.